

“The algorithm knows what I normally look at”: Assessing algorithm awareness and engagement

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Abstract

Existing quantitative research on algorithm awareness, engagement and intervention focuses on Facebook users and lacks insights from other social media platforms. In this study we analyze these questions in a sample of Instagram users. We disseminate a survey to a representative sample of Instagram users to quantify awareness for different socio-demographic categories and explore engagement types. We find that higher frequency of interaction with the social platform correlates with better algorithm awareness. We also find that more aware users, privy to Meta’s use of data, are more concerned with privacy. These findings indicate further investigation on larger sample populations is necessary to extrapolate on the links between algorithm awareness and engagement and draw significant conclusions.

Author Keywords: Algorithm awareness, algorithm engagement, algorithm perception

Introduction

Social media users increasingly receive curated, personalized news. Users of all ages from the US and UK mostly rely on Facebook for news, however, users age 18-24 rely more heavily on Instagram for news than other age groups.[\[1\]](#) Evidently, the algorithms curating the news have power over what we perceive on our feed.[\[2\]](#) More concerning, in recent news, is that Meta, formerly known as Facebook and Instagram’s parent company, has hit the front page of news cycles for their use of curation, personalization, and filtering algorithms for the sake of profit.[\[3\]](#)

In 2016, Instagram announced a switch from a chronological ordered feed to an algorithmically driven one. The introduction of the Instagram algorithm was met with push back and a demand for returning to a chronological feed. Like other social media platforms, little is known about how Instagram’s algorithm works. According to Instagram, six factors determine what is displayed on the Instagram feed: interest, recency, relationship, frequency, following and usage[\[4\]](#). Although this provides some qualitative information on factors used to curate, no architectural information is given on how these factors are implemented in the algorithm. Furthermore, in general, social media users are unaware of algorithms working in the background[\[5\]\[6\]](#), curating the information they see on their social media feeds.

In general, there have been an array of research and journal articles written concerning conceptual[\[7\]\[8\]\[9\]](#) and qualitative[\[10\]\[11\]](#) analyses of social networks, perception of algorithms, functioning of algorithms, awareness of algorithms, and user behavior in interaction with the

algorithmic feed on social media platforms. Although there is vast amounts of literature regarding qualitative and conceptual analysis of the subject matter, there are few papers that specifically design analysis around quantitative measures.[\[12\]\[13\]\[14\]](#) Fewer focus on qualitative and quantitative measures regarding Facebook.[\[5\]\[15\]\[16\]\[17\]](#) Previous literature on algorithm awareness regarding Instagram, focus on user opinions of curation algorithms[\[18\]\[19\]](#) and qualitative analysis of algorithm awareness[\[20\]\[21\]](#).

Generally, social media users are unaware of the algorithms curating their feed, thus extending to Instagram. Although quantitative studies of algorithm awareness have emerged for Facebook users in recent years, studies geared towards Instagram users are lacking. For this study, we aim to add our little drop of quantitative analysis into the scientific bucket of knowledge by: (1) quantifying algorithm awareness of Instagram users and (2) qualitatively analyzing user engagement on Instagram based on levels of algorithm awareness. Given there is little quantitative analysis on algorithm awareness of Instagram users, this study proceeds from an exploratory research approach. To this end, we set to empirically analyze algorithm awareness in a sample population and find correlations between user demographics such as gender, CRI students, and highest level of education.

Methods

We pulled methodologies from literature assessing levels of algorithm awareness of Facebook users[\[2\]\[15\]](#) to create five closed-ended survey questions for the evaluation of algorithm awareness amongst Instagram users. Sixteen closed-ended questions and eleven open-ended questions were created to evaluate user engagement on Instagram. Questions to collect demographic information (e.g. age, gender, level of education, etc) were included in the survey. Our rationale for the feasibility of including modified questions from previous quantitative studies regarding Facebook — sibling platform to Instagram and also owned by Meta — is the assumption that Instagram will have similar curation, personalization, and filtering algorithms.

Our study targeted social media users through an online Google form [survey](#). The profile of the targeted audience included ‘young people’ aged 18 to 40, who used or were familiar with Instagram as a social network. The survey was dispersed through communication tools from the CRI (e.g email, google drive) and through social media platforms (e.g. Instagram, Facebook) in order to reach diverse communities. Survey respondents were encouraged to share the survey link with others (e.g family, friends, co-workers, etc.) The survey was conducted anonymously to protect the privacy of respondents. Survey data was accessible through the Google forms platform. The [raw data](#) was pulled into an excel spreadsheet and then formalized into a data set in Python.

First step in our analysis is to define algorithm awareness and algorithm engagement. Based on existing quantitative literature[\[5\]\[15\]\[16\]\[17\]](#), algorithm awareness was defined as the ability to perceive or the knowledge that there is an algorithm at work responsible for curating tailored experiences on a social network. Algorithm engagement was defined as any behavior linked to engaging or attempting to manipulate Instagram’s curation algorithm — be it through negative actions (e.g. blocking, unfollowing), positive actions (e.g. liking, following, archiving), or

accessing hidden features.

Algorithm awareness was quantified by grading 5 closed-ended questions for algorithm awareness based on survey respondents' answers. Correct answer(s) or partially right answers to these questions were determined by the algorithm functions and factors described in the *TechCrunch*[4] and by Instagram[22]. Grades numerically represent respondents' algorithm awareness levels. For statistical analysis, resulting algorithm awareness grades were analyzed by the following demographic groups: gender, CRI students, and level of education. Each correct answer counts for 1 point towards the final grade. The questions are as follows:

1. If I want to see less of a certain kind of content, I can:
 - a. Block an account that has the content I don't want to see
 - b. Unfollow
 - c. Hide
2. Do you think these functions affect the content you are later presented with?
3. Can you rank them in order of importance?
 - a. Shares
 - b. Likes
 - c. Comments
 - d. Saves
4. In 2016 Instagram ended the chronological timeline on your homepage feed. Now posts appear in (a)_____ order based on (b)_____.
 - a. (a) random activity, (b) randomized factors
 - b. (a) random activity, (b) number of followers an account has
 - c. (a) priority, (b) content you are most likely to interact with'
 - d. (a) priority, (b) sponsored content
5. When I explore a page from a link posted in a friend's story, it affects:
 - a. The traffic count on the page linked
 - b. My friend's story will be showed more widely
 - c. 'The content I will later be presented with on Instagram
 - d. The content I will later be presented with on Facebook

Algorithm engagement was analyzed by breaking down responses to closed-ended questions into percentages. Common and recurring themes on algorithm engagement were extracted from responses. Answers to the closed-ended and open-ended questions were neither right nor wrong, only qualitative. Algorithm awareness grades correlated to algorithm engagement types.

Results

The Algorithm Awareness of Survey Respondents

The mean of all the survey respondents is 2.25 out of 5. Figure 1 depicts the overall awareness grade distribution amongst the respondents.

Fig. 1 : Algorithm awareness grade distribution of respondents'. The mean grade is 2.25/5

Algorithm Awareness by Demographic Groups

In order to delve into the analysis of the awareness, we associated respondents' grades for different subsamples: CRI students, gender and level of education.

I. Algorithm awareness by gender

Among the 107 respondents, 64 identified as female and 43 identified as male. The mean algorithm awareness grade for respondents who identified as females is 2.25. Regarding males, the mean is 2.18. (Figure 2b)

(a)

(b)

	Female	Male
Algorithm awareness mean	2.25	2.18

Fig. 2 : Algorithm awareness by gender: (a) grade distribution; (b) mean grade for males and females

II. Algorithm awareness: CRI students vs. Non-CRI respondents

The CRI students represented 52 respondents of the 107 responses. 55 respondents were individuals not associated with CRI. As shown in Figure 3b, the mean algorithm awareness grade of the CRI students is 2.19. The mean of the non-CRI respondents is 2.31.

(a)

(b)

	CRI Students	Non-CRI respondents
Algorithm awareness mean	2.19	2.31

Fig. 3 : Algorithm awareness grade (a) distribution; and (b) mean for CRI students and non-CRI respondents

II. Algorithm awareness by highest level of education

Among all the respondents, 17 respondents completed high school, 39 respondents attained a bachelor's degree, 37 have a master's degree and 4 completed a PhD as the highest

level of education. The mean algorithm awareness grade for the respondents who completed high school is 2.26. The mean for those who completed a bachelor's is 2.28, master's 2.32 and PhD 2.20 (Figure 4b).

(a)

(b)

	High School	Bachelor	Master	PhD
Algorithm awareness mean	2.26	2.28	2.32	2.20

Fig. 4 : Algorithm awareness grade by highest level of education: (a) grade distribution and (b) mean for high school, bachelor's, master's, and doctorate degrees

Perceptions of Algorithm Functions:

I. Are some accounts better served?

In this open question, 50.8% of the respondents expressed they did not perceive this bias in the algorithm. 16.9% of respondents expressed the view that algorithms served certain accounts better than others, however offered no elaboration on why or how. 18.5% observed it and claimed to understand this process on their own through observation and logic. Finally 13.8% claimed to have been informed through media or other Instagram users. (Figure 5)

The Instagram algorithm better serves certain types of accounts. Were you aware of this? If yes, how?

Fig.5 : Responses to the open question "The Instagram algorithm better serves certain types of accounts. Were you aware of this ?"

II. The content you see is changing, do you know how ?

The content presented to Meta users is curated through a user's interaction with the application[2][4]. 14.1%% of the survey respondents never noticed any particular changes in their feeds, some respondents stated a clear "No". While 2,8% claimed to have observed these changes they assumed the changes were made at random. 18,3% didn't elaborate on how they think this change was made. 64,8% of respondents expressed that they were both aware of changes as well as attributed those changes to their interaction with the social media platform. (Figure 6) Indeed, some respondents had a clear notion about the algorithm fonctionnement "*It is based on things that I've liked/shared/saved in the past*", some other respondents had a more broad picture on how this content had been recommended : "*Because of an AI analyzing my tastes*".

Have you ever noticed changes in the kind of content presented to you ? If yes, can you explain the changes and why they occurred ?

Fig.6 : Responses to the open question “Have you ever noticed changes in the kind of content presented to you?”

User’s Engagement and Their Level of Algorithm Awareness

I. Algorithm awareness grade and frequency of use

Algorithm awareness grades were broken down according to the engagement habits of respondents— where engagement is defined as time spent on Instagram as well as accessing positive (likes, comments, saves), negative (blocking, muting), and hidden features (privacy). The grade mean for respondents who spend 4 to 5 hours per week on Instagram is 2.54, respondents spending 1 to 3 hours per week are at 2.349, and those spending less than 1 hour, the mean is 2.345 (Figure 7a). Figure 7b represents the grade distribution by hours spent on Instagram within a week. In Figure 7c, the grade distribution is represented for respondents’ based on how often they use Instagram per week vs. time spent per day on Instagram.

(a)

(b)

	Less than 1 hour per week	1 to 3 hours per week	4 to 5 hours per week
Algorithm awareness mean	2.345	2.349	2.54

(c)

Fig. 7 : Algorithm awareness grade by frequency of use: (a) distribution and (b) mean; (c) grade clusters according to the number of hours spent on Instagram per week vs. times per day Instagram is used

II. How Do Users “Fix” the Content Shown ?

When respondents were asked about actions they took to “fix” or curate the content proposed by the algorithm, 36.2% answered they take no actions to change it. 23.2% will avoid interacting with content they do not like. 15.9% will take steps to hide undesired content. 14.5% of respondents will unfollow profiles or hashtags posting content they don't wish to see or interact with. Finally, 5.8% will report (signal) content as inappropriate, and 4.3% will block it. (Figure 8)

Fig. 8: Responses to the closed question “What actions have you taken to “fix” the content showed to you?”, given the choices: Nothing, Hide, Ignore, Unfollow, Block, or Report

Algorithm Awareness and Privacy Concerns

I. Algorithm awareness and privacy care

The respondents were asked if they are concerned with privacy on Instagram. 20 respondents answered that privacy was a concern and 12 respondents declared privacy wasn't a concern. The mean algorithm awareness grade of respondents concerned with privacy is 2.52 and 2.25 for those who aren't.(Figure 9a). Fig. 9b shows the grade distribution regarding the privacy concerns.

(a)

(b)

	Concerned with privacy	Not concerned with privacy
Algorithm awareness mean	2.52	2.25

Fig. 9 : Algorithm awareness grade by privacy concern: (a) distribution and (b) mean

II. Why are users (not) concerned about privacy ?

Reasons for concern or unconcern about privacy in Instagram are shown in Figure 10. 5.6% responded that they have “nothing to hide”, 8.3% said that “you only live once”, meaning that they do not worry about what can happen in the future, 2.8% consider that as the app is free, their data is being used, although this person consider herself as a “conscious consumer” of Instagram, finally 13.9% are not concerned because they don’t share content on Instagram, “Don’t post much. And already agreed to have data used by service” . On the other hand, 33.3% don’t want other people to see their private content, one of them stated : “I’m a blogger and I need to protect my privacy”, 27.8% don’t trust social media companies “Don’t want my data to be sold to compagnies” and 8.3% are concerned with their personal data “Because I know that using social media means there is no privacy, I am aware the media uses my data and I know I cannot really do much about it if I want to continue using it” .

Fig. 10 : Responses to open question “Why are you/aren’t you concerned with privacy?”

III. Privacy can take away the Instagram experience ?

In Figure 11, 76.8% of the respondents answered that having a private account wouldn't take away their experience on Instagram. Also, 13% think that it depends and 10.1% think it does take away the experience.

Do you feel like an account set to private can take away from your experience on Instagram?

Fig. 11 : Perception on how setting your account to private takes away from the Instagram experience

Discussion

Our data analysis has revealed the following themes of our exploration:

I. Awareness and socio-demographic factors

Three socio-demographics factors were assessed during the survey : gender, level of education, and CRI students. These factors can be correlated with the awareness grade. When grouping respondents by gender, the female mean was calculated as slightly higher than the male mean but not significantly so. The mean of CRI students is not better than for the overall population. In fact, their awareness grade is slightly lower. Finally, there seems to be a slight upward trend of algorithm awareness with increasing levels of education. This trend could not be extended to the PhD, due to the fact that there were not enough PhD respondents to observe any trend.

II. Respondents who were more concerned with privacy had a higher level of algorithm awareness

As stated in the results, the mean awareness grade of survey respondents is 2.25. The grade of respondents concerned with privacy is 2.52, for those who are not, the grade is 2.25. The results indicate that respondents who are more concerned with privacy tend to be more aware of the algorithm mechanics on Instagram. The open question showed that the privacy concerns stemmed from the cognizance of social media companies' use of personal data to personalize content. One respondent expressed in response to the question 'Why are you/aren't you concerned with privacy?' : *"I am aware the media uses my data and I know I cannot really do much about it if I want to continue using it."*

Indeed, several news headlines regarding Meta's use of curation, personalization, and filtering algorithms for the sake of profit have had an impact on the relationship between the social media company and its users—or rather consumers. When asked about whether respondents were concerned with privacy one individual expressed their frustration by stating: *"Don't want my data to be sold to compagnies"*. Pulling from the qualitative data collected from open-ended questions it is clear that respondents voicing concerns surrounding privacy were aware of Meta's business practice regarding the collection and sale of data collected from users. Consequently, privacy concerns seem to have risen in this sample population.

III. Respondents who spend more time on Instagram have a more accurate understanding of algorithmic mechanisms

As observed in Figure 7a. respondents spending more time on Instagram have a higher awareness grade. Respondents spending 4 to 5 hours a week on Instagram have a mean grade of 2.52 which is higher than the mean of the survey respondents. The open questions provided insight into how respondents interacted with the social media platform, as well as how they attempted to engage with the algorithm itself. As previously mentioned, six factors determine what is displayed on a user's Instagram feed: interest, recency, relationship, frequency, following and usage[4]. Indeed, respondents stated that they were aware of some of these factors influencing their feed. When asked if respondents knew why certain accounts were suggested to them in the explore section they answered: *"[...]Algorithm based on what I interact with [...]"*, *"the algorithm is knowing what I normally look at, stop scrolling or which topics I comment on or interact with"*. As reported in Fig. 5, 18.5% of the respondents became aware of the algorithm mechanisms by using and interacting with the application. When asked if survey respondents were aware of how certain accounts were served better than others one respondent shared : *"I noticed while using it"*. Another reason for this awareness was attributed to information shared on the application. This is the case of 13.8% of the respondents. Again, when asked 'The Instagram algorithm better serves certain types of accounts. Were you aware of this? If yes, how?' some respondents shared : *"an Instagram post I saw explained it"; "thanks to [...] influencers complaining about [...] the algorithm..."* This phenomenon could explain why respondents that spend more time on Instagram would have the perception of being more aware of the algorithm as well as more familiarized with its mechanisms.

IV. Shortcomings

i. “Average” Algorithm Awareness.

While our algorithm awareness grade offered new empirical insight for Instagram specifically, there are clear limitations to the quantitative findings. The algorithm awareness grades of our sample population cannot represent an “average” grade for any population outside the scope of our study. In order to extrapolate these findings it would be necessary to collect data from a larger sample population and then standardize an average algorithm awareness grade.

ii. Comparative population awareness doesn’t allow to interpret the results

Although we have slight differences in the algorithmic awareness grade mean between males and females as mentioned in Figure 1b, we do not have data allowing us to interpret this result. Given that the samples are relatively small, albeit well balanced (64 females and 38 males), we don’t know that the observed differences are statistically significant and should lead to conclusions. The survey does not entail any question allowing us to characterize different behaviors for different subsamples. In order to include such questions in the survey, conducting interviews prior to designing the survey or after its first analysis would have been helpful.

A similar difference is observed for CRI students (52 respondents) vs non CRI respondents (55) as shown in Figure 2a. The better mean algorithm awareness grade of non CRI respondents might be related to a selection bias: our survey was shared with CRI students via emails and to others vastly through Instagram. Our results show that more time spent on Instagram means a better algorithm awareness (Figure 7c) - which could explain our non CRI recruits’ performance.

iii. The engagement according to the population

In order to minimize the amount of people leaving the survey before it is completed, we have designed the engagement questions towards the end of it as open-ended non-mandatory questions. This allowed us to have a qualitative approach and gain insight to identify different categories of behaviors, but did not allow for a quantitative analysis. It is thus not possible to compare different population subsamples’ algorithm engagement as with the grade computed to quantify algorithm awareness.

Speculation

Following the analysis we have conducted, several further studies building upon our work could lead to interesting findings

I. Algorithms and political views and engagement

We could lead a quantitative comparison between Facebook and Instagram because they are sister social media platforms. More specifically, leading a thematic quantitative analysis would allow us to investigate more in depth the politically-charged defiance towards Meta we have identified in the open-ended questions. How do people's political views impact their behavior on social networks? Are people who are more politically-minded more aware of algorithms' mechanisms?

II. Information sources about algorithms

It would be interesting to get more insight into how people obtain information about algorithms: whether they draw conclusions from what they are presented with on Instagram or if they actively seek out information, and if so from what sources. Also to know whether it is most heavy Instagram users who are most diligently researching the application's inner workings or not.

III. Instagram algorithm awareness in literature

Quantitative analysis specific to measuring and analyzing algorithm awareness in Instagram users does not lend itself to direct comparisons. Due to the lack of quantitative studies on Instagram algorithm awareness, it is impossible to use the results from our sample population to compare against other sample populations that could potentially offer up an "average" awareness.

IV. Evolutions of algorithm engagement

This research field is fast evolving due to the modifications made to the design of the algorithms as well as the new features launched that can drastically change the behavior of users. Recently, Instagram has introduced a feature which allows users to switch to a chronological feed. This is following years of pushback on the algorithmic feed and a demand from users to return the chronological feed. As Instagram tests the new feature, users will be presented with the option to curate their feed based on their feed layout preference. It begs the question of what portion of users will actively choose chronological, algorithmic or a mix of both and for what reasons.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, H. Herman, N. Savelyeva, B.E. Estrada Chavez, L. Ruvalcaba, M. Dalle; **Data curation**, M. Dalle, L. Ruvalcaba; **Formal analysis**, B.E. Estrada Chavez, M. Dalle, L. Ruvalcaba, H. Herman; **Investigation**, B.E. Estrada Chavez, L. Ruvalcaba, M. Dalle, H. Herman, N. Savelyeva; **Methodology**, L. Ruvalcaba, B. E. Estrada Chavez ; **Software**, H. Herman, N. Savelyeva, B.E. Estrada Chavez; **Visualization**, H. Herman, N. Savelyeva; **Figures**, M. Dalle, B.E. Estrada Chavez, L. Ruvalcaba; **Writing—original draft**, M. Dalle, B.E. Estrada Chavez, L. Ruvalcaba, H. Herman; **Writing—review and editing**, B.E. Estrada Chavez, L. Ruvalcaba, H. Herman, M. Dalle; **Project administration**, H. Herman, N. Savelyeva, B.E. Estrada Chavez, L. Ruvalcaba, M. Dalle .

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